

English Classroom for SLA of Students and Small and Medium Entrepreneurs in Thailand

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Abstract—The English competence of Thai people was examined in the context of knowledge of English in everyday life for Small and Medium Entrepreneurs (SMEs), and also integrated with Second language acquisition (SLA) students' classroom. Second language acquisition was applied to the results of the questionnaires and interview forms. Levels of the need on English used for SME entrepreneurs in Thailand, satisfaction on joining the street classroom project were shown to be significantly high for some certain language functions and satisfaction. Finding suggests that the language functions on etiquette for professional use is essential and useful because lesson learned can be used in the real situation for their career. Implications for the climate of the street classroom are discussed.

Keywords—English classroom, second language acquisition, Small and Medium Entrepreneurs, Thai students.

I. INTRODUCTION

TOURISM plays an important role in many aspects. It causes higher employment; many people have a job, more product and service income affecting to economic revenue. For the society aspects, working in local communities can reduce evacuation or relocation during their time away from agriculture. This tour also gives the community a sense of pride in their cultural traditions. The role of tourism has been developing steadily since the year 1919 to the present. The government has seen it as major hand on bringing enormously money to the country with minimal investment. However, Shortage of personnel in the field of tourism, both quantity and quality, is also available. Especially, the overall weakness of Thailand is English for communication with the tourists. A main area that is popular for the tourist in Bangkok is Banglumpu area in the metropolitan area. There are no clear boundaries of space with consisting of main communities: Buddhist monastic community (Wat Sungwetsayaram, Wat Intharawiharn, Wat Sarm Praya, Bovornrungsri), Chakkraphong Mosque. Other communities are TrokKoasarn, Trokkiannivart, TrokKai Jae, Soi Rammabuth etc. Original condition of Banglumpu area is attractions and commercial matters.

Future than this, Banglumpu area is still cultural resources because it is Royal County of many royal families and followers who are craftsmen and artists. Later it has been changed in location image, economy and society seen from convenient transportation, business extension, migration for

business running or residents for workforce and education purposes.

Besides this, it is also near the main attraction of Thailand, Temple of the Emerald Buddha, so there are many backpackers from around the world who want to touch Thai traditional life with cheaper guesthouse renting, convenient transport to other attractions areas. These tourist activities make lots of local income distribution such as guesthouse owner, restaurant, tour boots, souvenir shop, massage and spa services and etc. These business owners make high profit to community leading to country economic development. From the survey on tourist activities informs that these entrepreneurs are lack of communicated skill with their customers, especially, English language.

English is the main language used for communication between the various nationalist most countries. It has been defined as an international language or universal language (Global Language) playing a key role in political, economic, educational and other areas in the world. So those who have knowledge of English, find jobs more easily. There are various job opportunities and better salaries. More likely to progress, they meet the needs of large organizations, both nationally and internationally. However, main task of university is pedagogy so this research is the integration of English classroom and small business by improving English both students and entrepreneurs.

English pedagogy focuses on student improvement or student center by teacher just be like the facilitator in nowadays. Thus, the curriculum has specification (six questions) as follows [1]:

1. Why does the student need to learn?
2. Who is going to be involved in the process?
3. Where is the learning to take place?
4. When is the learning to take place?
5. What does the student need to learn?
6. How will the learning be achieved? Or What learning theory will underline the course?/What kind of methodology will be employed?

And it leads to main three points in English classroom management: 1) language description 2) learning theories and 3) need analysis. In addition, the target needs consist of three main things; they are necessities or what learners learn to achieve the goal, lacks or what the learners do not know, and wants or what learners want to learn.

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II. OBJECTIVES

1. To study English communication of entrepreneurs in Small and Medium Enterprise in Khao San – Sam-Sen Road areas.
2. To analyze the skills and the ability to use English for communication of entrepreneurs in Small and Medium Enterprise in Khao San – Sam-Sen Road areas.

III. METHODOLOGY

The researcher conducted the study with the following procedure:

A. Research Procedure

1) Meeting to Plan the Research

The first stage, the researchers gathered together to plan the operation: devised a conclusion in the form of research, process of project implementation, the division of responsibilities for preparation of the working group. Since this research emphasizes on the integration of teaching- the use of English, students and communities together, it requires students to act as a research assistant. They should be knowledgeable in the field of research so it needs to educate students with research training for 6 hours. In addition, the researchers studied the documents and research related to the book, publications, computer networking, the book prepared by the Department of Labor for information on designing lessons.

2) Students Examine Data from a Real Context

The researchers explained the details and procedures of the research project with Business English Students participate as a research assistant, before assigning students to the area for the real context to search the information on the survey need to use English for entrepreneurs and small businesses in Khao San – Sam-Sen Road areas. It is to find out that any small entrepreneurs who wish to join the project including to which topic/content to learn.

3) Create English Lessons for Tourism for Entrepreneurs

The researchers convened to classify the business and organized the English teachers for each student group of business types and the business owners that students made the contacts to join the project. Teachers and students jointly prepare lessons by using dialogues underlying the research jointly built as the centerpiece. Each group adapted dialogues according to their own business involved such as vocabulary, expression, grammar structure depending on their product and service scope. These lessons were edited by the native speaker for suitable level and contexts, and did the final lessons for the students to practice with the small medium business entrepreneurs in Khao San – Sam-Sen Road areas.

4) Training students

Teacher groups prepare students by training them in each group conversations lessons provided for the students approached the small business entrepreneurs at their business site. It focuses on pronunciation, vocabulary, stress and

intonation, technique and other important phrases or sentences including the accuracy of the language, practice fluency in speaking with and psychological and climate stimulated learning. Then let them practice role-play with the dialogues of selling and buying things in pairs. This step is to prepare students before they will train the entrepreneurs at business site such as street areas or in the shops.

5) Training Entrepreneurs and Small and Medium Businesses

Students arrange the process to transfer the knowledge and practice of English in the purchase - sale of goods and services of each entrepreneur by day and time convenient. In practice the use of English to small businesses entrepreneurs; students use the training side by side: they sit with the entrepreneur to explain and practice the lessons together until they can use English in simulated situation. This is an important step of this study that Nunan says "although learner strategy training has entered the popular pedagogical imagination, with special journal issues, conferences, and textbooks devoted to the application of strategy training to language leaning, there is still relatively little research into the effect of strategy training on learners and learning processes." [2]

6) Video Filming

After the entrepreneurs accomplished the training to use the English language in the purchase - sale of goods and services, students take a video of the purchase - sale of goods and services in the real situation between the shopkeepers and people who use English to communicate.

7) Project Evaluation

An evaluation made by the satisfaction of participants to question the satisfaction of entrepreneurs who have received the knowledge of English, including overall satisfaction with the project.

8) Deliver Work within Teacher Group

Student delivered the lessons containing dialogues that they use with the entrepreneurs in the real situation varied by product or service list in each group. They also collect the satisfaction questionnaires and observation form that records what they perceive during the project running on.

B. Population and Sampling Group

The sampling groups are 1) 30 entrepreneurs who own the small-medium business in Khao San – Sam-Sen Road areas 2) 70 junior students majoring in Business English, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, and registering in for English for Marketing and Advertising 1.

C. Research Tools

Data are collected by 1) a survey questionnaire for need analysis on English language knowledge of entrepreneurs in Khao San – Sam-Sen Road areas. The questionnaires consist of three parts: part 1 general information, part 2 the need on English usage for entrepreneurs in Khao San – Sam Sen Road areas, part 3 the topics for training. Another tool is a

behavioral observation form for the students to record activities during they train the entrepreneurs.

D. Data Collection

Collecting data process contains three steps as follows:

1) Pre-Teaching

When a student has an appointment date and time convenient to train entrepreneurs to use English in buying - selling their products and services successfully, students will go to the appointment of the operator before the appointed time to train entrepreneurs to use English. Students are required to observe the situation around, waiting for a vacancy on the sale of - available for the training, at that time the students observe the real situation in the sale of goods and services.

2) While Teaching

These students teach the entrepreneurs side by side with English vocabulary and structures on buying - sales and service of each store until they can speak more confidently, correctly and fluently, and use suitable vocabulary and expressions.

3) Post-Teaching

After the training, the entrepreneurs do the satisfaction questionnaires to project evaluation. The students also record their observation form on what they can observe during they do this activities.

E. Analyze Questionnaires

Analyze questionnaires to evaluate the entrepreneurs' satisfaction.

F. Report the Results

Write the report paper.

IV. RESULTS

A. General Information

There are 35 samplings: 76.1% are females, 23.9% are males. The average age is 31-35. Most of them finished below bachelor degree 71.7%, bachelor degree 23.9%. The enterprise contains two main types; they are product and service. The former is food (café, desert, food made by customer ordering), drinks, fruit, cloth, and etc. The latter is shoe-repaired shop, hair dressing shop, and etc.

B. Need on English

From questionnaire for need analysis, entrepreneurs need to use English in sales/service at 84.8 %, having problem in the use of English for careers at 73.9 %, want to learn English to communicate in a career at 63.0 %. And 76.1% of them want to join the university training on the use of English. It is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Entrepreneurs' Need on Improving Their English

TABLE I
SKILL AND ABILITY ON USING ENGLISH BEFORE AND AFTER THE TRAINING

Topics	Before training	After training
1. Pronunciation	Pronounce wrong sounds: Goos morning.	Pronounce more right words as: Good morning. They can pronounce the final sound as /k/ in drink. They can link the final sound of words in a sentence as - It's a kind of....
2. Word position in sentence	They switch the word position: What I can do?	Vocabulary position in a sentence more correctly-for example: What can I do for you?
3. Fluency	They cannot naturally speak and understand what they say, so it lakes of fluency.	They can speak more fluently and more suitable expressions such as: - Would you prefer hot or cold mocha? -Do you prefer.....?
4. Numbers of vocabulary and expressions	Numbers of vocabulary and expressions are limited.	They know more numbers of vocabulary and expressions : piece, change , fried egg, congee, etc.
5. Ability on explanation	They use short words for explaining their products for example: ingredients - pig, fish, chicken instead of mixed meat.	They can use more words and expressions: - Would you like blended coffee? - I'm sorry. It's a fixed price.
6. Language level on service the customer	They use words or sentence as: What do you want?	They can speak more politely with their customer: What would you like, sir / ma'am?
7. Awareness of customer's cultures	Using expression on saying thank you: Thank you very much.	They can add more words or expressions as : Thank you very much. Have a nice day.

C. English Function Topics

From the questionnaire, the topics that they want to improve in English using are as follows:

- Greetings- greetings and responses
- To say thank you and acceptance

- Farewell
- The price of the trade
- Details of product
- The customer care

- Vocabulary, expression related to business: product / service for each enterprise.
- Telling directions
- The General information: Small talk

D. English Skill of the Entrepreneurs

It is found that skill and ability on using English before and after the training of entrepreneurs better in all aspects : 1) pronunciation more correctly, 2) word position in sentence 3) fluency, 4) numbers of vocabulary and expressions 5) Ability on explanation 6) language level on service the customer 7) beware of customer's cultures as in Table I.

V. CONCLUSIONS

English for a specific purpose (ESP) is useful for sale product and service both students and entrepreneurs according to [3] investigates how current applied linguistic research into the nature of call centre communication breakdown in business processing outsourcing (BPO) sites such as India and the Philippines, can impact English communications training program content and design for this industry.

English for communication of entrepreneurs, especially for a small and medium enterprise (SME), through students training is also useful in case of both students and entrepreneurs improvement in their English together. Teachers' role plays as a facilitator and possesses knowledge that students do not yet have. Knowles's idea [4] gives much greater emphasis to innovation and the generation of new knowledge over the acquisition of traditional knowledge. This assumption is ultimately counterintuitive in the context of language learning adding that before any new knowledge is created, there must be *something* out there to be discovered and experimented with. He also says that the everyday language students encounter in or out of the classroom seems to be appropriate, and there is much that is traditional in it. The English class is not limited just in the classroom but it is also near the street or real situation at the enterprise environment.

Thus, it is like learning English on the street. The entrepreneurs have their own vocabulary and expressions that according to what business they run and have the change to practice their English at their shop while they are training English with the students. This is as English on the street that Chern and Dooley use the four resources model of literate practices to systematically map some of the potential of literacy walks in multilingual, multimodal linguistic landscapes. They suggest tasks and teacher questions that might be used for the explicit teaching of reading during and after literacy walks [5]. As Mckay says the educational goal of learning an international language is to enable learners to communicate their ideas and culture to others [6].

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